

Execution Time Prediction via Lightweight AI for Edge-Fog-Cloud Task Offloading

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Abstract—Edge-Fog-Cloud systems utilize offloading to shift workload from less powerful edge nodes to more powerful central nodes in fog and cloud. However, existing approaches for offloading decisions rely on simplified execution time estimations, such as static values or linear time-per-byte (TPB) approximations. However, many tasks show a highly variable execution time behavior, with more complicated relationships to the original request, leading to suboptimal scheduling of tasks and hardware usage.

We propose a method for predicting the execution time for different execution nodes, based on a lightweight AI model. The approach is based on a multi-output feedforward neural network, able to predict the execution time for all heterogeneous compute nodes in a single pass. Numerical and categorical features are extracted from the request as model input. The resulting prediction was then integrated into a cost model for the final offloading decision. The proposed concept was then evaluated on different task categories: Tasks with a more linear relationship, such as applying an image filter, tasks with a more complex relationship, such as GPS routing, as well as hybrid complexity tasks, where the execution time is not only influenced by the request size, but also more complex relationships. For tasks with a hybrid relationship, the proposed approach was able to decrease the overall offloading cost by 14.66% compared to using TPB approximation. This includes the sub 0.3ms prediction latency. Even for tasks whose execution time depends nearly linearly on the request size, the proposed approach was equal to TPB. On a mixed-task dataset, the overall cost was decreased by 5.59% compared to TPB.

Index Terms—Offloading, Edge-Fog-Cloud Continuum, Heterogeneous Computing, Execution Time Estimation

I. INTRODUCTION

Driven by the rapid development of connection technologies such as 5G or 6G, distributed systems increasingly scale across several layers of the edge-fog-cloud continuum [1], by shifting work from the edge to higher layers. In such systems, a single central instance responsible for the execution of all tasks is no longer sufficient. Instead, the specific advantages of the different layers are utilized to improve system performance. The close proximity of edge devices provides reduced transmission latency, while fog and cloud instances offer a higher processing throughput at higher transmission latency and cost for hosting the devices and bandwidth [2].

Static offloading targets often underperform because link quality can fluctuate between requests. This problem is already well explored in literature [3], with approaches taking into consideration the quality of the channel, the size of the

request, and trying to predict future connection behavior [4]. However, even with perfect channel and size predictions, offloading decisions remain suboptimal because they ignore per-request execution time variability. Current approaches use a static execution time or a linear approximation based on the request size to estimate the execution time. And while this is sufficient for some tasks, such as image processing tasks, where the execution time scales largely linear with the number of pixels ($O(N)$), the same approach fails for more complex tasks, where the execution time is defined by the relationship between different parameters of the request. One example of such a use case is the generation of a navigation route between two GPS points.

This leads to less-efficient IoT systems, as the offloading decision does not take into consideration the capabilities of the different, heterogeneous compute nodes on a per-request basis. We therefore propose a method to reduce offloading costs by improving the accuracy of the offloading decision. Our approach utilizes a lightweight AI model to predict execution time on a per-request basis for each available compute node. This enables a more intelligent trade-off between transmission latency and computational throughput, leading to substantial performance gains, particularly for tasks with complex execution patterns, while still being competitive on less suitable, linear tasks. The main contributions of this paper are: 1) A novel lightweight AI-based single-pass execution time prediction model for heterogeneous, distributed systems, with fundamentally different hardware architectures (x86, ARM, RISC-V). 2) A comprehensive evaluation demonstrating the impact on different classes of tasks.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows: section II reviews related work. section III characterizes the task used for evaluation. section IV then describes the concept, followed by the evaluation in section V. The paper then finishes with the discussion in section VI and the conclusion in section VII.

II. STATE OF THE ART AND BACKGROUND

Task offloading is a fundamental mechanism for resource management in distributed systems, and as such, has been the subject of extensive research. The core challenge involves balancing the trade-off between communication cost and computation time. Current approaches utilize a time per bit approach, with different offloading targets having different capabilities

and therefore process each task with a different speed [5]. Especially for mobile networks, the network connection speed and quality are major decision factors [6], [7].

While many approaches focus on these conditions, prediction-based approaches have been explored. Examples are an LSTM-based prediction approach for task offloading by Tu et al. [8]. A time-per-byte (TPB) approach is used to calculate the execution time for each task for local or offloading. An LSTM-based approach is used to predict future tasks and calculate costly offloading decisions, before requests actually arrive, possibly reducing latency. However, the LSTM is not used for the execution time-prediction itself.

Chen et al. [9], [10] describe an approach to predict future behavior, such as CPU load and temperature, as well as task throughput, based on their previous behavior and the task type to be executed. This, however, does not take into consideration the unique character of the task to be offloaded, besides the task type itself, and requires feedback from the compute node to the node responsible for orchestrating the offloading decision. Also, the prediction is unique to each compute node and must be repeated for each suitable candidate node.

Given these limitations in execution time prediction for offloading, considering approaches from other relevant domains becomes valuable.

Liu et al. [11] proposed a scheduling policy for assigning serverless function tasks on CPU cores with different frequencies to exploit how some applications scale with CPU frequency, while others are mainly bottlenecked by other factors, such as network connectivity. For predicting the execution time for different CPU frequencies, they use some characteristics of the request, such as the file size for upload, download, or compression tasks, and the number of rows and columns for generating an HTML/XML table. They were able to achieve power savings of up to 8.5% without impacting tail latency. They then utilize a linear model for prediction, and their total latency prediction takes around 0.2ms.

Another domain where execution time prediction plays a major role is in High-Performance Computing (HPC). Here, users often have to request a certain amount of time for their computational tasks. Errors in this prediction can lead to increased wait time in the queue, decreased system utilization, or premature killing of tasks by the scheduler. A major difference to offloading in IoT is that the execution time of tasks is often in the sub-second to second range, while for HPC, the execution time is in the range of days. Typically used models for execution time prediction are XGBoost, Linear Regression, or neural networks [12]. However, due to the large variance of tasks in HPC, where most tasks are completely unique, prediction often relies on the submitting user and historical data for a single cluster, [13]. As the execution time of the prediction is less important for HPC, due to the typically long execution times.

In summary, while task offloading and various predictive techniques are well explored, existing approaches for estimating the task execution time for offloading decisions rely on simplistic models that cannot capture the complete task-

specific complexity for all task types. Predictive models in other domains, such as serverless or HPC, address different scales, constraints (prediction latency), or task granularity. Therefore, a gap exists for a lightweight execution time prediction to optimize the offloading decision in edge-fog-cloud systems. This research aims to address this gap by introducing an AI model to predict the execution time for tasks based on their unique characteristics.

III. TASK CHARACTERIZATION

This section details the tasks used for evaluation and establishes the requirements for a node-specific multi-output prediction model. The six selected tasks represent a spectrum of computational behaviors and are grouped into three different classes, **linear**, **complex**, and **hybrid**. The requests for each task are detailed in Table I.

Linear Tasks: These tasks show an execution time that largely scales linearly with the request size. Two image processing tasks from the OpenCV library, Gaussian Filter and ORB (Oriented FAST and Rotated Brief) feature detection, and one text processing task, text summarization, from the Natural Language Toolkit (NLTK) are used.

Complex Tasks: For these tasks the execution time has a non-trivial relationship with input parameters that cannot be captured by the request data size. GPS-Navigation, which utilizes BRouter as a backend for graph-based route calculation, and Heat-Diffusion, a 1D simulation where the execution time depends on the number of grid points and time steps, are used.

Hybrid Tasks: These tasks have some correlation between the execution time and the request size, but also other characteristics have a non-trivial impact on the execution time. The example for these tasks is an N-Body simulation, where the execution time is influenced by the number of bodies (data size) and the selected simulation mode, which alters the computational complexity.

TABLE I
PARAMETERS OF THE USED TASKS

Task	Class	Parameters
Gauss-Filter	Linear	Image Size, Kernel Size
ORB	Linear	Image Size, Max features, Pyramid Levels, FAST Threshold
Text-Summarization	Linear	Algorithm, Input Size, Output Length (Min/Max), Output Ratio
GPS-Navigation	Complex	Start / End Location, Vehicle Profile, Alt. Route, Output Format, Waypoint Export
Heat-Diffusion	Complex	Grid Points, Time Steps, Boundary/Initial Condition
N-Body	Hybrid	Dimensions, Bodies (Position, Speed, Mass), Simulation Mode, Central Mass, Time Steps

One key observation is that the performance ratio between different compute nodes for the same request is not always constant, even when the task is executed without specialized accelerators. This behavior is illustrated in Figure 1, which shows the execution time of various requests for the N-Body

simulation on two different compute nodes, one AMD-based workstation and a RISC-V-based Single Board Computer.

Fig. 1. Relative Execution Time of the N-Body tasks between an AMD64 and a RISC-V node

While a general positive relationship exists, the occurrence of multiple high-variance clusters with a linear relationship reveals that a linear scaling factor is insufficient. One request could be 20x as fast on the AMD64 machine, while another request for the same task could be 50x as fast. This non-linear relationship across heterogeneous hardware shows the need for a multi-output prediction model that can predict the execution time for each compute node independently.

IV. CONCEPT

This section details the proposed method for a task-aware offloading method based on a multi-output prediction model. It begins with an overview of the overlaying modular system architecture and the overall cost model used for decision making in subsection IV-A. Subsequently, it provides a detailed description of the core component in subsection IV-B: the AI-based execution time prediction module, including its feature engineering process and model architecture.

A. System Architecture and Cost Model

The offloading decision framework, shown in Figure 2 is designed with a modular architecture, by separating distinct cost factors into independent modules, these consist of the **Execution Time Prediction Module**, the **Transmission Module**, and the **Operational Cost Module**. The **Offloading Cost** orchestrator combines the output of these modules to calculate a final score for each potential offloading target. While this work’s primary contribution is the Execution Time Prediction module, the other modules, marked in grey, are included to form a complete and evaluable offloading solution.

The **Transmission Module** provides an estimate for the network round-trip time required to send the request to the compute node and receive the result. For the scope of this evaluation, a static transmission time is assumed for each offloading target. The **Operational Cost Module** represents

Fig. 2. Offloading Architecture Overview

the operational or monetary cost associated with utilizing a specific hardware resource, not captured by the other modules. This would include costs such as maintenance, energy, or cloud-provider costs. A static value is assigned to each node. The ultimate offloading decision is based on a unified cost score, which combines the different cost factors. As the execution time for different requests on the different hardware nodes can vary by a wide margin, a non-linear scoring function is used to combat outliers more heavily. The total cost for offloading a task to a specific node is calculated through the following equation:

$$Cost = (1 + T_{Transmission})^{W_{Transmission}} + (1 + T_{Execution})^{W_{Execution}} + (1 + C_{Operational})^{W_{Operational}} \quad (1)$$

Here, $T_{Transmission}$, $T_{Execution}$, and $C_{Operational}$ represent the values from the Transmission, Execution Time Prediction, and Operational Cost module, respectively. Adding 1 to each term ensures the base is always greater than one, preventing issues with zero values. The weights (W) allow for tuning the relative importance of each factor and control the non-linearity of the penalty; a higher weight results in a steeper penalty for larger cost factors.

B. AI-Based Runtime Prediction Module

The central contribution of this concept is the Execution Time Prediction Module. This module addresses the limitations of existing approaches by using a lightweight neural network. This enables the better prediction of execution times for each available compute node based on the specific characteristics of each request.

1) *Rationale and Feature Engineering*: As established in section III, a TPB model is insufficient for tasks with complex parameter execution time relationships. On the contrary, a full simulation of the actual task would incur prohibitive latency, negating the potential benefits of the prediction. A lightweight AI model serves as an effective middle ground, capable of learning complex, non-linear relationships, while still being able to maintain a low prediction overhead.

To achieve this, each request is first processed through a feature extraction step. Key parameters that influence the execution time are extracted to serve as inputs for the model. This reduces the dimensionality of the input and, consequently, the computational complexity of the prediction. These parameters can be numerical (e.g., image size, simulation time steps) or categorical (e.g., selected algorithm, simulation mode). Features can be either taken directly from the request or extracted through trivial functions, such as the size of a request parameter.

The extracted features undergo a pre-processing pipeline before being fed into the model:

- **Categorical Features:** These are converted into a numerical format using one-hot encoding.
- **Logarithmic Transformation:** For numerical features that span several orders of magnitude or exhibit a skewed distribution (such as data size), a $\log(x + 1)$ transformation (\log_{1p}) is applied in addition to using the normal value. This helps the model learn from the features more effectively by compressing the range of large values.
- **Normalization:** Both the original, as well as any logarithmic features, are normalized to ensure better capturing of different scales in the input features.

For instance, for the N-Body task, the categorical simulation mode is one-hot encoded, while numerical features like dimension and time steps are normalized. The size of the bodies parameter, being highly variable, is both normalized and log-transformed to create two separate input features.

2) *Prediction Model Architecture:* The prediction model is a multi-output feedforward neural network (FNN). This architecture was chosen as it is well-suited for regression tasks and can learn complex mappings from request features to execution time. Critically, the multi-output structure allows it to predict the execution time for all potential compute nodes in a single forward pass, which is essential for minimizing the prediction latency.

Fig. 3. Prediction Model Architecture

The network’s topology, shown in Figure 3, is generated as follows. The input layer size, N_{in} , is the sum of features from three sources: one-hot encoded categorical parameters, normalized numerical, and log-transformed numerical parameters. The architecture is designed to terminate in an output layer of size N_{out} , corresponding to the number of compute nodes.

The core of the architecture is made up of dynamically sized hidden layers. The sizes of these hidden layers are powers of two, derived from a sequence of integer exponents. This exponent sequence begins at $E_{start} = \lceil \log_2(N_{in}) \rceil + 2$ for the first hidden layer and progresses towards an end exponent of $E_{end} = \lceil \log_2(N_{out}) \rceil + 1$. The sequence steps by one at each subsequent layer, allowing the network’s width to contract or expand based on the input and output dimensions. To ensure the network can capture complex relationships, a minimum of two of these hidden layers is enforced; if the generated sequence is shorter, it is padded at the beginning with the E_{start} value. For tasks where a more complex network is required, the width of the network can be changed through a scaling factor. This structure of hidden layers is followed by the final, dense output layer of size N_{out} . This architecture provides a robust starting point that scales systematically with input/output dimensions, avoiding manual tuning for each task.

To account for the wide dynamic range and skewed distribution of execution times across heterogeneous nodes, the model is trained to predict the \log_{1p} -transformed target values. This standard technique has the critical benefit of aligning the loss function with the offloading objective; it implicitly prioritizes relative error, thus forcing the model to be more precise for the faster, more desirable compute nodes. The network’s output is converted back to the linear domain using the inverse $exp(x) - 1$ transformation.

V. EVALUATION

This section details the evaluation of the proposed concept. It begins with an overview of the experimental setup, followed by an analysis of the offloading decision itself and the impact of the offloading decision, and closes with an analysis of the multi-output prediction model.

A. Experimental Setup

The experimental validation of the proposed offloading concept is based on the six tasks grouped into the four classes (linear, hybrid, complex, as well as a combined all class) as described in section III. For each task, a dataset of a minimum of 17000 requests with randomly generated parameters. This ensures that both the complete parameter space is covered, and that execution behavior is available for all different hardware platforms, information that existing trace datasets are missing. The parameter ranges were constrained to ensure individual task execution times did not exceed a 30-second threshold on the slowest compute node. The GPS-Navigation model, due to the task’s complexity, uses a width scaling factor of 2.

The four different compute nodes in Table II were used to represent a typical heterogeneous edge-cloud-fog hierarchy,

TABLE II
EXPERIMENTAL COMPUTE NODES AND ASSOCIATED COSTS

Role	Hardware Platform	Latency	Cost
Cloud	AMD Ryzen 9 9950X	124ms	1.5
Fog	NVIDIA Jetson AGX Orin	83ms	1.0
Edge (ARM)	Raspberry Pi 3B+ 1GB	0ms	0.0
Edge (RISC-V)	StarFive VisionFive 2	12ms	0.0

from resource-constrained SBCs to high-performance cloud instances, represented by an x86 workstation. The latency values for the fog and cloud systems are based on typical latencies for a driving vehicle [14]. The ARM-based edge node, as the slowest of the four compute nodes, is also used as the task source. The RISC-V-based compute node has an additional latency to model internal communication within a single physical location, such as a vehicle. The assigned cost factor is dimensionless and represents a combination of real-world constraints, such as direct monetary costs, energy costs, and opportunity costs for occupying shared resources. For the cost calculation in Equation 1, the weights were set to $W_{Transmission} = W_{Execution} = 1.2$, and $W_{Operational} = 1.0$. The chosen configuration places a slightly higher, non-linear penalty on latency and execution time compared to the static operational cost. $C_{Operational}$ is 1.3 for the fog node and 1.4 for the cloud node, while the edge nodes both have cost of 0, to represent the higher costs of maintaining these offsite nodes.

B. Analysis of Offloading Decision

This evaluation compares the proposed approach, the optimal offloading decision, a TPB, a Round Robin (RR), as well as a static offloading to the cloud compute node-based approach, for all four task groups, based on the realized cost of the decision method. Figure 4 compares the distribution of costs for all five offloading approaches for both the hybrid and the all task groups. The prediction latency is added to $T_{Execution}$ and is based on the maximum execution time of all models on the edge ARM compute node.

The minimum cost possible is 3, due to the used cost function. The Round-Robin based offloading shows both, the highest mean cost, as well as the highest maximum offloading cost. As expected, the naive Round-Robin (RR) strategy yields the worst performance, exhibiting the highest mean and maximum cost due to its failure to account for either node capability or task characteristics. Similarly, the static cloud offloading approach, while benefiting from high processing speeds, is fundamentally limited by its high transmission latency and operation cost, resulting in a cost distribution heavily skewed towards a floor determined by these. Both the proposed and the TPB-based approach have a higher maximum cost than the optimal solution. But the proposed approach is able to reduce the maximum cost by nearly a factor of two for the all task group and by a factor of nearly 4 for the hybrid task. Also, the distribution of the proposed approach follows the optimal solution closer than the TPB-based one.

TABLE III
OFFLOADING COST BY DATASET AND APPROACH.
DIFFERENCE TO OPTIMAL OFFLOADING COST

Statistic	Optimal	Proposed	TPB	Cloud	RR
<i>All Tasks</i>					
Mean	3.79	0.69%	6.32%	21.91%	23.57%
Median	3.55	0.37%	24.94%	28.57%	27.72%
P99	5.33	3.38%	1.10%	0.00%	224.54%
P95	4.84	0.61%	0.55%	0.00%	28.18%
P5	3.02	0.01%	0.06%	50.71%	0.66%
<i>Complex Tasks</i>					
Mean	4.21	1.17%	9.88%	10.83%	32.61%
Median	4.48	0.30%	1.23%	1.82%	1.81%
P99	5.73	3.81%	0.00%	0.00%	341.34%
P95	5.17	1.96%	0.00%	0.00%	93.50%
P5	3.12	0.01%	41.64%	45.89%	3.91%
<i>Linear Tasks</i>					
Mean	3.54	0.35%	0.39%	29.73%	15.76%
Median	3.25	0.29%	0.29%	40.47%	36.72%
P99	4.72	0.20%	0.19%	0.00%	20.56%
P95	4.69	0.08%	0.08%	0.00%	4.61%
P5	3.02	0.01%	0.00%	50.86%	0.50%
<i>Hybrid Tasks</i>					
Mean	3.69	0.57%	15.32%	24.64%	27.39%
Median	3.40	0.45%	33.93%	34.13%	32.19%
P99	5.08	0.37%	21.38%	0.00%	218.44%
P95	4.83	0.25%	2.94%	0.00%	52.85%
P5	3.02	0.01%	1.35%	50.62%	1.08%

Table III shows the detailed results for all offloading methods and task groups. Columns, other than the optimal one, show the difference from the optimal. The proposed approach consistently outperforms all baselines. For the All Tasks group, it achieves a mean cost just 0.69% above the theoretical optimum, a significant improvement over the TPB approach's 6.32%. The benefit is most pronounced for Complex and Hybrid tasks, where the mean cost is reduced by 8.71 percentage points and 14.75 points, respectively, compared to TPB. This demonstrates the model's ability to capture non-linear execution time relationships that simpler models miss. The proposed approach is also able to significantly reduce the worst-case performance for the hybrid tasks. Although the TPB or static cloud offloading approach is able to beat the proposed approach slightly in other task sets in the 99th percentile. The proposed approach is able to capitalize on low-cost opportunities (P5) for complex Tasks, where unnecessary offloading is costly. At the same time, the proposed concept is also able to slightly beat TPB on mean execution time for linear tasks, by being more resistant to slightly nonlinear behavior. Conversely, for the most demanding tasks (P99), the TPB and static cloud strategies have a slight edge, as the optimal decision for these outliers is almost always the highest-performance node. This focus on optimizing the broader task distribution, rather than just the extremes, is what drives the proposed method's superior overall mean performance. The reduced 5th percentile performance of the proposed approach for linear tasks compared to TPB, is a direct consequence of the added prediction latency.

(a) All Task Groups

(b) Hybrid Task Group

Fig. 4. Comparison of Cost for Different Offloading Decision Methods

C. Impact of the Offloading Decision

Figure 5 shows the selected offloading target for the optimal, Proposed and TPB based approaches for the hybrid, complex and all task groups. The behavioral differences driving the performance gap, can be seen. The TPB method over-utilizes the fog and cloud nodes, often unnecessarily offloading tasks where the network latency outweighs the execution speedup. This highlights a key flaw in size-based heuristics: an inability to discern when local execution on a slower edge device is more efficient. In contrast, the proposed approach demonstrates more balanced and intelligent resource allocation, selecting edge nodes more frequently, thereby resembling the optimal distribution more closely. This leads to better overall system efficiency and avoids unnecessary network traffic. This can also be seen in Table III for the complex tasks, where the 5th percentile of TPB is close to the cloud one. In contrast, the proposed approach is able to better utilize these local resources. This leads to an overall more equal use of all available compute resources.

D. Prediction Model Performance

A critical aspect of the proposed concept’s viability is the latency overhead of the AI model itself. The prediction must be significantly faster than the potential savings it provides. Table IV confirms that this condition is met and shows the number of trainable parameters for each prediction model, and the mean prediction and execution time for both edge

Fig. 5. Endpoint Selection Frequency by Offloading Method and Task Group

compute units. The data shows that the prediction latency is negligible compared to both task execution times and network latencies. The maximum observed mean prediction time on the slowest edge device (ARM) was just 293 μ s. In the worst-case scenario relative to task execution time (Text-Summarization on the RISC-V node), this overhead accounts for a mere 0.19% of the mean execution time. When compared to the 83 ms network latency for fog offloading, the prediction overhead

constitutes less than 0.36%, validating its practicality for real-time offloading decisions.

TABLE IV
TASK MODEL AND PERFORMANCE FOR EDGE RISC-V ($_V$) AND EDGE (ARM) $_ARM$
TIME IN ms

Model	Params	T_{P_ARM}	T_{P_V}	T_{E_ARM}	T_{E_V}
Gauss	312	0.168	0.168	737	730
ORB	1032	0.205	0.210	580	566
Text-Sum.	1096	0.248	0.248	167	130
GPS-Nav.	3852	0.281	0.294	3978	2720
Heat-Diff.	1128	0.293	0.289	1243	1199
N-Boby	1128	0.252	0.252	1356	1163

VI. DISCUSSION

The evaluation demonstrates that the proposed AI-based execution time prediction approach can significantly improve offloading decisions in heterogeneous edge-fog-cloud systems. The primary strength of the approach lies in its ability to learn and predict complex, non-linear relationships between task parameters and execution time, a capability that TPB models inherently lack. This leads to a more intelligent allocation of resources, as seen in the endpoint selection analysis in Figure 5, where the proposed method more closely mirrors the optimal distribution by avoiding unnecessary offloads to high-latency nodes for tasks that are better suited for local execution. This is directly responsible for the substantial cost reductions observed for the complex and hybrid task groups.

However, the approach’s viability is contingent on the prediction overhead being negligible compared to the potential gains from offloading. Specifically, the prediction must be significantly faster than the network transmission, which itself must be faster than the execution for offloading to be beneficial ($T_{Prediction} \ll T_{Transmission} < T_{Execution}$). The evaluation confirms that for typical network latencies, this condition holds true, validating the practicality of the concept.

From a practical deployment perspective, the proposed concept requires an initial data collection and training phase. A representative dataset must be generated for each task type to train an effective prediction model. Furthermore, the feature engineering process is a manual task. Representing a one-time engineering cost for each newly added task.

The current model architecture also presents limitations in terms of system dynamics and scalability. The multi-output network is configured for a defined number of compute nodes. To accommodate new hardware, placeholder outputs can be provisioned during the initial design phase. The model can then be adapted to a new compute node (or to reflect changes in an existing node’s hardware or software) through incremental online learning. Moreover, the proposed concept, much like the TPB baseline, does not explicitly account for real-time system state variables such as network congestion, fluctuating CPU load on shared resources, failed requests, or temporarily unavailable compute nodes. These simplifications allow for a more specific evaluation, but at the same time can be integrated into a holistic offloading decision process,

which is out of scope of this work’s focus on the execution time prediction component.

It is also important to acknowledge the classes of tasks for which this approach is not suitable. For tasks with a near-constant execution time or those whose execution time is primarily content-dependent (e.g., depending on the number of objects in an image), the shallow feature extraction used in this concept would be insufficient. Capturing such dependencies would necessitate a more powerful, and likely higher-latency, AI model for the feature analysis itself, which could violate the core requirement of low prediction overhead.

We have chosen a feed-forward neural network, due to its multi-output prediction in a single forward pass and suitability for online learning. While other models, like gradient boost, might yield higher accuracy for some tasks, they require separate models per node, increasing prediction latency. Therefore, if the distance between an optimal allocation and the feed-forward neural network increases, testing other model architectures for these tasks could provide benefit, although neglecting the architectural advantages.

Finally, the evaluation utilized a cost model with fixed transmission and cost factors. While these are approximations of real-world variable conditions, this highlights the robustness of the core contribution. The overall cost calculation in Equation 1 is inherently subject to uncertainty from all its components. By substantially reducing the uncertainty and prediction error associated with the task execution time, the proposed method improves the accuracy of the overall cost score, leading to more reliable and efficient offloading decisions even when other parameters are not perfectly known.

VII. CONCLUSION

This paper introduced a novel method to improve offloading decisions in edge-fog-cloud systems by utilizing a lightweight, AI-based execution time prediction model. The evaluation demonstrated that by learning the complex, non-linear relationships between a task’s parameters and its execution time on different hardware nodes, the proposed approach significantly outperforms traditional offloading strategies. For mixed-task workloads, the difference to an optimal offloading decision was reduced by 5.63 percentage points compared to a TPB model. The improvement was most pronounced for tasks with complex and hybrid execution time characteristics, where the proposed method achieved a cost within 0.57% of the theoretical optimum and reduced the mean cost by 14.75 points over the TPB baseline, all while accounting for the minimal prediction overhead. The analysis confirmed that the model’s prediction latency is negligible, validating its practicality for real-time applications.

The presented approach, while effective, lays the groundwork for tackling more complex, dynamic applications. The most significant direction for future research is to extend this predictive framework to support stateful services. This is a non-trivial challenge, as the offloading decision must then also model the considerable overhead of state synchronization and execution across heterogeneous compute nodes, as well as the

impact of the state on the runtime. The high dimensionality of an application's state further highlights the need for an automated feature selection process.

Successfully deploying such a system for stateful tasks in a real-world environment would necessitate further enhancements. For instance, creating a holistic end-to-end cost view would require integrating predictions for real-time network latency, including state synchronization cost and the size of the response. Similarly, for long-term viability, online and few-shot learning techniques could be explored to allow the architecture to better adapt to new compute nodes and evolving task types.

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